

Pink Aesthetics-A Case Report of Gingival Depigmentation Using Electrocautery Method

Yadav P¹, Azmi S², Yadav V³

Received on: 17 October 2024; Accepted on: 11 January 2025; Published on : 19 February 2025

Assistant Professor¹
Department of Periodontics
Career Post Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

Assistant Professor²
Department of Periodontics
Career Post Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

MBBS³
Dr. RMLIMS
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

Abstract

The color of gingiva varies in different individuals and is assumed to be correlated to ethnic and racial backgrounds. Melanin is the natural pigment causing gingival pigmentation. Gingival hyperpigmentation is common in most of the individuals. Though it is harmless but it is a serious aesthetic concern in individuals especially with gummy smile. In such cases gingival depigmentation is a treatment of choice when individuals demand it for their aesthetic satisfaction. This article shows gingival depigmentation for the correction of hyperpigmented gingiva using electrocautery.

Keywords: Melanin, Hyperpigmentation, Gingival depigmentation, Aesthetic dentistry.

Introduction

A beautiful smile is not only accompanied by a beautiful dentition but also by an aesthetic gingiva. Hence, gingival tissues are very crucial part of a pleasing smile¹. Gingival hyperpigmentation is very common in most of the individuals. It may range from physiologic reasons (racial pigmentation) to pathologic reasons (Addison's disease, melanoma, Kaposi sarcoma etc.)². The gingival color primarily depends upon size and number of vasculature, degree of keratinization, epithelial thickness and the pigments within the gingival epithelium.³ Melanin is the most frequent brown colored, non-hemoglobin derived natural pigment resulting in gingival pigmentation. Carotene, reduced hemoglobin and oxyhemoglobin are also the pigments contributing to the normal color of the oral mucosa⁴. The degree of pigmentation varies from one individual to another and is mainly governed by the melanoblastic activities. Melanocytes are the dendritic cells of neuroectodermal origin present in the basal layer and the spinous layer of the gingival epithelium⁵. The process of pigmentation includes an activation phase, synthesis phase and expression phase. In the activation phase, melanocytes are stimulated by factors like sunlight, stress hormones etc. and leading to the production of melanocyte stimulating hormone (a chemical messenger). In the synthesis phase, these melanocytes synthesize melanin in the organelles called melanosomes. This proc-

ess takes place when the enzyme tyrosinase converts the amino acids into dehydroxyphenylalanine (DOPA) molecule. Tyrosinase then converts DOPA into secondary chemical dopaquinone. Dopaquinone, after a series of reactions converted into eumelanin (dark) or pheomelanin (light). In the expression phase, the melanosomes transferred to keratinocytes which are the skin cells located above melanocytes in the epidermis. After this, the melanin color eventually become visible on the surface^{4,5,6}. The earlier studies have shown that there is no significant difference exists in the density of distribution among the light skinned individuals and dark skinned individuals^{7,8}. Gingival pigmentation is presented as a diffuse, purplish discoloration or brown and light brown or black patches or striae of irregularly shaped. The attached gingiva is the most common site of such pigmentation^{9,10}. Gingival hyperpigmentation is harmless but its correction is demanded by most of the individuals for their aesthetic satisfaction as many individuals consider their dark colored gums to be unesthetic¹¹. Gingival depigmentation is a periodontal plastic procedure which include removal or reduction of hyperpigmentation of gingiva by using various methods such as conventional methods like

Access this article online

Website : www.healtalk.in

Quick Response Code

How to cite this article : Yadav et al. -Pink Aesthetics-A Case Report of Gingival Depigmentation Using Electrocautery Method HTAJOCD 2025

surgical scalpel technique, gingival abrasion, chemical methods using chemical agents like phenols, alcohols, ascorbic acid, cryosurgery, by electrocautery and laser depigmentation. By understanding the distribution of pigmentation, one can help in deciding the better treatment strategies^{11,12}. In this article gingival depigmentation was done to achieve satisfactory aesthetic outcome by using electrocautery.

Case Report

A 22 year old male patient reported to the Department of Periodontology with the chief complain of blackish gums while smiling owing to poor aesthetics (fig A). Patient's historical accounts indicated that it had existed since childhood. Overall, the patient's oral hygiene was healthy & good. Initially, scaling was done and gingival depigmentation using electrocautery was opted as treatment modality. Following the administration of local anesthetic solution loop, diamond shaped electrode and needle electrodes were used (fig B). Coagulation was done using ball electrodes. Controlled brushing strokes were used with light gradual movement of the tip. Repeated and prolonged application of electrode to the tissues was avoided as it causes undesired tissue destruction. A clean field with minimal bleeding was maintained (fig C). The surgical area was covered with a periodontal dressing (coe-pack) for 1 week (fig D) and postoperative instructions were given. For the management of pain, analgesic was prescribed. The pack was removed after 1 week and the surgical area was examined. The healing was uneventful without any postoperative complications (fig E). The gingiva appeared pink and healthy giving a normal appearance (fig E). The patient was very much impressed with the pleasing aesthetic outcome.

Figures (A-E)

A. Pre- Operatively

B. During Surgery

C. After Surgery

D Coe-pack Placed

E. Post Operatively (after 1 week)

Discussion

Esthetic dentistry is a recently emerging branch¹³. In normal healthy persons, gingival color has wide variations¹⁴. The foremost indication for depigmentation is individual's demand for the improvement of esthetics¹⁵. It can be achieved using various methods such as scalpel scraping method, gingivectomy, chemical cauterization, gingival abrasion, cryosurgery, electrosurgery and laser therapy^{5,7,16}. The use of scalpel for depigmentation is most economical but causes unpleasant bleeding¹⁷. Electrocautery has its own limitations as its prolonged use causes undesired tissue destruction due to heat accumulation. However, minimal bleeding is there while using electrocautery¹⁸. The technique selection should be based on the clinical experience and patient's acceptance & affordability^{18,19}. In this particular case, the depigmentation was done using electrocautery and gave satisfactory results. We found this method relatively simple, versatile, effective and required minimum time and effort.

Conclusion

Hyperpigmentation of gingiva is a common aesthetic problem^{4,7}. Various treatment modalities available for depigmentation of gingiva which yields better results¹¹. However, the most important factor for determining the treatment of ging-

ival hyperpigmentation is the type of pigmentation, expertise of clinician, patient's acceptance of treatment procedure, its prevalence and its aesthetic importance^{19,20}. In future, even if gingival repigmentation occurs in this patient, the same procedure could be repeated as repigmentation is a common problem in such cases²⁰. However, the depigmentation performed in this case was successful and patient was also fully satisfied with the results. Hence, it can be concluded that depigmentation of gingiva using electrocautery is simple, easy and provides minimal discomfort to the patient with aesthetically pleasing results.

References

1. Dummett, C.O: Oral pigmentation. First symposium of oral pigmentation. *J Periodontol* 1960;31:356
2. Cicek Y, Ertas U. The normal and pathological pigmentation of oral mucous membrane: a review. *J Contemp Dent Pract*. 2003;15;4(3):76-86.
3. Dummett CO, Barends G. Oromucosal pigmentation: an updated literary review. *J Periodontol*. 1971;42(11):726-36.
4. Perlmutter S, Tal H. Repigmentation of gingival following injury. *J periodontal* 1986;57:48-50
5. Dummett CO. Oral pigmentation. *J periodontal* 1960;31:356-60
6. Shafer WG, Hine MK, Levy BM. Text book of oral Pathology. Philadelphia: WB Saunders co; 1984; pp. 89-136
7. Szako G, Gerald SB, Pathak MA and Fitz Patrick TB. Racial differences in the fate of melanosomes in human epidermis. *Nature* 1969;222:1081
8. Tal H. Landsberg J and Koztovsky A: Cryosurgical depigmentation of the gingiva - a case report. *J. Clin Periodontol* 1987;14:614-7
9. Roshna T, Nandakumar K. Anterior Esthetic Gingival Depigmentation and Crown Lengthening: Report of a Case. *J Contemp Dent Pract* 2005; (6)3:139-147
10. Almas K, Sadig W. Surgical treatment of melanin pigmented gingiva; an esthetic approach. *Indian J Dent Res*. 2002;13(2):70-3
11. TK Pal, KK Kapoor, CC Parel, K Mukharjee. Gingival melanin pigmentation-a study on its removal for esthetics. *J Indian Soc of Periodontology*, 1994;(Special issue)3:52-54
12. Begamaschi O, Kon S, Doine AI, Ruben MP. Melanin repigmentation after gingivectomy: A five year clinical and transmission Electron Microscopic Study in Humans. *Int Journal of Periodontics & Restorative Dentistry*, 1993;13(1):85-92
13. Hirschfeld I and Hirschfeld L. Oral pigmentation and method of removing it. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Path*. 1951;4:1012
14. Dummett CO and Bolden TE. Post surgical repigmentation of the gingival. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Path*. 1963;16:353
15. Tamizi m, Taheri M. Treatment os severe physiologic gingival pigmentation with free gingival autograft. *Quintessence Int*. 1996; 27 (8) :555-8
16. Trelles MA. Verkruysse W, JM Segui, and Udaeta A. Treatment of melanotic spots in the gingival by Argon laser. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg*. 1993; 51:759-61
17. Gnanasekhar JD, Al Duwairi YS. Elecrosurgery in Dentistry. *Quintessence Int* 1998;29:649-54
18. Ishida CE, Ramose Silva M. cryosurgery in oral lesions. *Int J. Dermatol* 1998;37:283-85
19. Ozbayrak S, Dumly A and Ercalik YS. Treatment of melanin pigmented gingival and oral mucosa by CO2 laser. *Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol. Endod* 2000;90:14-15
20. Atsawasuwan P, Greethong K, Nimmanon V. Treatment of Gingival hyperpigmentation for esthetic purposes by Nd: YAG laser: Report of 4 cases. *J Periodontol* 2000;71:315-321